

The roles of morphology and molecules in modern systematics

Habilitation thesis for attaining a Venia Docendi
in the field of Biological Systematics
at the University of Bern

Seraina Klopstein, PhD

General Introduction	2
Summary and discussion.....	5
Species discovery and the roles of morphology and DNA	5
Phylogenetics for evolutionary research.....	8
Advances in molecular dating.....	11
List of papers included in habilitation thesis	15
References.....	16

General Introduction

The scope of systematics

Systematics is the study of the diversity of organisms and the relationships among them through time. It comprises the discipline of taxonomy whose task it is to describe organisms, provide scientific names for them, build reference collections (especially for the name-bearing type specimens), and suggest a comprehensive classification (Michener et al. 1970). But systematics goes beyond taxonomy by also addressing the relationships between organisms through phylogenetics, i.e., building the tree of life. These phylogenies can then be used to address evolutionary questions. The scope of systematics is thus quite broad and it underpins and touches upon almost all other biological fields. Alpha-taxonomy, or the taxonomic study of species and subspecies, has a close relationship with population genetics and speciation research, and it provides a reference system in the form of scientific names for all organismic research branches, especially ecology and conservation biology. Classification or beta-taxonomy aims to classify organisms into higher ranks such as genera, families, orders, classes and kingdoms (Mayr 1942). It nowadays relies on phylogenetics which in turn is based on insights from molecular evolution and methodologies borrowed from statistics. Phylogenetics provides the foundation for disciplines as diverse as comparative biology, adaptation research, evolutionary biology, medicine, and many more. And where phylogenies are used to infer the past, systematics is also in close exchange with palaeontology.

Systematics and evolutionary theory

Systematics and especially taxonomy are among the oldest branches of the biological sciences, with the first systematic approach to classification dating back to the famous work by Carl Linnaeus in the eighteenth century (Linnaeus 1758). Since then, systematics has undergone several profound changes due to advances both in theoretical and methodological areas. One such change was initiated by the publication of Darwin's "Origin of Species" and the ensuing realization that all organisms are related via ancestor-descendant relationships (Darwin 1859). The traditional, typological classification system was based on morphological diagnoses and the definition of type taxa to define higher ranks. But now voices were raised that called for a classification that reflects the evolutionary history of a group and thus would only contain natural, monophyletic groups which go back to an exclusive common ancestor. Once the reconstruction of evolutionary relationships obtained an objective basis in the form of algorithmic tools for phylogenetic inference (Hennig 1965, Felsenstein 1973, Felsenstein 1981), traditional classification was thus more and more combined with phylogenetic reasoning. There is still some debate about whether higher-level taxa should be defined based on type taxa or based on nodes in a phylogenetic tree (De Queiroz and Gauthier 1990, Nixon et al. 2003, De Queiroz 2006, Kuntner and Agnarsson 2006), and the codes of nomenclature do not (yet) contain the formal requirement of higher taxa to be monophyletic (International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature 1999, McNeill et al. 2012). Nevertheless, it is nowadays common practise to define taxa above the species rank so that they satisfy the criterion of monophyly.

Evolutionary theory also had an impact on how new species are described. After centuries of purely typological species descriptions, systematics has shifted to a new understanding of the act of naming a species: It is nowadays seen as the proposal of a testable hypothesis with reference to a

species concept (e.g., De Queiroz 2007). Accordingly, the description of a new species implicitly includes the statement that all individuals that are in accordance with a specific diagnosis belong to a species following either the biological (Mayr 1942, Mayr 2000), evolutionary (Wiley and Mayden 2000), phylogenetic (Wheeler and Platnick 2000), unified (De Queiroz 2007), or any other species concept. The diagnosis can contain morphological, molecular, behavioural, ecological or other features (Schlick-Steiner et al. 2010, Yeates et al. 2011), and new data can be used to refute the hypothesis. However, the actual naming of the species still follows the typological approach, i.e., the new name is linked to a type specimen and not to the species diagnosis; taxonomic names are thus to some degree independent of the species hypothesis. This becomes apparent when considering that even if the species hypothesis is refuted and a new hypothesis about the species circumscription proposed, the name might still be valid if it represents the oldest name for a currently valid species hypothesis. Many modern alpha-taxonomic works reflect this duality by separately describing the holotype (the reference specimen for the name) and the variation within the proposed species (e.g., Klopstein 2014).

Molecular techniques revolutionizing the field

Traditionally, systematics was based on morphology, with the addition of ecological, behavioural, and distributional data. This applies both to species descriptions and phylogenetics. The discovery of the structure of DNA (Watson and Crick 1953) and later of the polymerase chain reaction (PCR, Saiki et al. 1988) led to a veritable revolution in most biological disciplines, and systematics is no exception. The availability of DNA characters influenced all systematic levels. In alpha-taxonomy, there are now proponents of largely automated species delimitation approaches that rely on molecular data alone (Hebert et al. 2003a, Vogler and Monaghan 2007), but the majority of the taxonomic community argues in favour of a combination of molecular, morphological and other data in iterative or integrative taxonomy approaches in order to establish robust species hypotheses (de Carvalho et al. 2008, Schlick-Steiner et al. 2010, Yeates et al. 2011).

In phylogenetics, DNA sequences have largely replaced morphology as the main source of data. Morphological data is deemed less objective, more cumbersome to come by, and more difficult to model accurately (Scotland et al. 2003, Wiens 2004, Gaubert et al. 2005). It is thus usually only included if molecular data is not available (Yassin et al. 2008) or is indecisive (e.g., Glenner et al. 2004, Wahlberg et al. 2005, Quicke et al. 2009). Even in combined analyses of both data types, molecular characters often so greatly outnumber morphological data that the signal of the later is pretty much drowned among the molecular signal (but see Wortley and Scotland 2006). This effect is likely to increase in the near future. Until now, traditional Sanger sequencing of short stretches of DNA which have been amplified by PCR was the predominant way of obtaining sequence data, but next-generation sequencing techniques are gaining momentum also in systematics as they become available and affordable for non-model taxa (Mamanova et al. 2010, McCormack et al. 2013). Morphology is thus likely to become even more marginalized in present-day phylogenetics. Concerning the inference of the past, the proposition of a molecular clock (Zuckerandl and Pauling 1962) further strengthened the link between molecular phylogenetics and palaeontology and initiated the steadily growing research field of molecular dating. However, as any molecular clock needs to be calibrated, morphology is still used in molecular dating study, even though usually in an implicit fashion (see below).

In parallel to the replacement of morphological by DNA characters for phylogenetics, stochastic approaches that rely on maximum likelihood have superseded parsimony methods (Felsenstein 1981, Ronquist and Deans 2010). These approaches rely on evolutionary models and bring a plethora of advantages over the parsimony framework, most of all by providing a full stochastic framework that allows for model testing. The evolution of DNA or protein sequences is deemed much easier to approximate with mathematical models, most of all Markov models, especially as the state space is finite and state labels are not arbitrary, which allows for generalizations that improve power and greatly simplify computation of these models. Morphological data was only made amenable for likelihood analysis later by the seminal work of Lewis (2001b, 2001a) who suggested a simplified Markov model for characters with an arbitrary number of states with arbitrary labels. Improvements on this basic model for morphology are scarce and not widely used (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck 2003, Alekseyenko et al. 2008). The development of morphological models, especially in the context of the highly flexible Bayesian statistics, still lags behind the theoretical and technical advances and represents one of the most important areas in current systematic research.

Own research and study group

I here use twelve studies ranging from alpha-taxonomy to phylogenetics and molecular dating to illustrate the roles of morphology and molecules in systematics, demonstrate the limits of current methods, and point to potential improvements and future research questions. The study group in most of these works are parasitic wasps from the family Ichneumonidae (Insecta, Hymenoptera). As pointed out rather eloquently by Jerry Coyne: "to a first order of approximation, all animals are insects" (from J. Coyne's blog at <https://whyevolutionistrue.wordpress.com>, accessed on 12 Jan 2016) (Fig. 1). Indeed, according to the last edition of the IUCN Red List (Vié et al. 2009), 950,000 or 58% of all described multi-cellular organisms (including animals, plants, fungi, and algae) are insects. This number and the proportion of the total will certainly rise quickly in the future, as insects are also the group for which the largest number of species still awaits discovery. Insect species richness is dominated by the "big four", i.e., the orders of the beetles (Coleoptera), moths and butterflies (Lepidoptera), flies and mosquitoes (Diptera), and bees, wasps, ants and relatives (Hymenoptera) (Fig. 1). Within Hymenoptera, the parasitic groups and especially the family Ichneumonidae are the unchallenged leaders of the list; 52% of Hymenoptera and 4.5% of all described species are parasitoid wasps (Aguiar et al. 2013). They feed internally (endoparasitoids) or externally (ectoparasitoids) on immature or adult stages of other insects or spiders to complete their larval development. Being at the top of the food web, parasitoids play a key role in almost every terrestrial ecosystem, and numerous species are successfully used in the biological control of pest insects.

Figure 1. Number of described species of multicellular organisms, of insects, and of hymenopterans. Data sources: IUCN Red List 2008 (Vié et al. 2009), Aguiar et al. (2013).

In the largest hymenopteran family Ichneumonidae, 24'281 species are currently described (Yu et al. 2012), but this is probably the group where current knowledge lags most strongly behind the actual diversity (Quicke 2012). Conservative estimates of the undescribed species richness in this family repeatedly exceed 100,000 (e.g., Gauld et al. 2002), which is more than twice the number of vertebrates (46,000 described species). This tremendous undiscovered species richness not only calls for increased efforts in the alpha-taxonomy of the group, but also makes it an ideal system to investigate diversification patterns. The large variety of parasitoid strategies that can be found in this group, from egg predators in spider egg sacks to highly specialized endoparasitoids of caterpillars and beetle larvae, and multiple transitions between parasitism ecologies such as endo- and ectoparasitism provide ample opportunity to test evolutionary hypotheses of adaptation and diversification.

This habilitation thesis contains three parts, each of which addresses a different area of systematic research, i.e., alpha-taxonomy, phylogenetics and evolutionary research, and molecular dating. For each of these, I give a brief summary of the current state of the field, including the current roles of morphology and molecules and focussing on approaches and issues exemplified or critically evaluated in my own work. The findings of each study are then explained and discussed with respect to future developments in systematics.

Summary and discussion

Species discovery and the roles of morphology and DNA

Background

Because of human activities and climate change, extinction rates on our planet are currently skyrocketing (Pimm et al. 2014), and many of the species that disappear have not been described yet, so we do not even know what we lose. This gap in our knowledge of the Earth's biodiversity is due to what has been coined the "taxonomic impediment", i.e., the shortage of taxonomic expertise where it is most sorely needed (Gaston and May 1992). Several ways to overcome the taxonomic impediment have been suggested, starting from the obvious approach of devoting additional funding to taxonomy (Wheeler 2005, de Carvalho et al. 2008) to the adoption of faster if less rigorous techniques via partial automation of the process of species recovery (Tautz et al. 2002, Frézal and Leblois 2008). DNA barcoding uses a 600 basepair portion of the mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase subunit 1 (CO1) gene to delimit and distinguish species; it has been used with great success in several groups where the match with established species hypotheses was found to be very high

(www.barcodeoflife.org; Hebert et al. 2003a, Hebert et al. 2003b, Hajibabaei et al. 2006, Gómez et al. 2007, Derycke et al. 2008, Smith et al. 2008). However, once barcoding studies began to include more closely related species and sampled larger geographic areas, reports of inconsistencies started to accumulate. Non-monophyletic gene-trees and failures of threshold-based delimitation methods were estimated in different studies to concern between about 10% and 30% of all species (Funk and Omland 2003, Meier et al. 2006, Bergsten et al. 2012). Another drawback of barcoding is that it can currently only be applied to relatively fresh specimens, even though some progress has been made with amplifying the barcoding locus from museum specimens. In any case, specimen availability is still much higher for morphological analyses, which can also consider old type specimens, and even though this issue might diminish with improvements in sequencing technologies, it today still puts a considerable constraint on taxonomic studies. In addition, many species today known to science have only been recorded based on single or very few specimens, and such singletons disturb automated species delimitation approaches (Lim et al. 2012, Ahrens et al. 2016).

Own work

My own work on questions around the species level ranges from morphological alpha-taxonomic studies including species descriptions to an evaluation of the barcoding approach in parasitic wasps and combined approaches to delimit species. Papers 1 and 2 of this thesis contain morphological revisions of the Diplazontinae from the Kuril islands, a volcanic island chain between Japan and Russian Kamchatka, and of the cremastine genus *Dimophora* from Australia, respectively. They include the descriptions of two and nine new species, respectively, and add to our very patchy knowledge of ichneumonid distribution patterns (Quicke 2012). As an example, I could report *Tymmophorus gelidus* Dasch from the Kuril islands, a species that has been described from the Arctic zones of the Northwest Territories and from Greenland (Dasch 1964). A single specimen has been recorded from Northern Sweden (Klopstein 2014), and the appearance of the species on the Kuril islands supports its circumpolar distribution. This finding is somewhat indicative of a general pattern for diplazontine wasps which show a very high proportion of species with multi-regional distributions (Manukyan 1995). The study on *Dimophora* (paper 2) is remarkable in that it overturned the current understanding of the centre of diversity of that genus which earlier was known only from seven species from the Holarctic and one from Costa Rica. The nine new species from Australia and reporting of a further two from this continent are exemplary for our lack of even basic data on ichneumonid diversity and distribution.

A combination of morphological and molecular characters was used in the revision of the Western Palearctic species of the ichneumonid subfamily Diplazontinae (paper 3). The Diplazontinae have only been revised in the Nearctic region, and identification keys for the European fauna are incomplete and often reflect outdated taxonomy. I thus revised the subfamily using discrete morphological characters and molecular data from two genes, the mitochondrial barcoding locus and the nuclear internal transcribed spacer 2 (ITS2). Studying about 12,000 specimens from 16 countries, I could revise the subfamily to include 99 species in the Western Palearctic, seven of which were newly described. Many types needed to be studied to assure correct interpretation of the species names, and a comparison to the North American fauna exposed many confirmed and potential synonyms. Illustrated identification keys to genera and species now allow secure determination of specimens from the Western Palearctic. Morphology and molecular data complemented each other very well in many cases where morphology-based species hypotheses could be confirmed by clear molecular differentiation. The latter is especially significant in the case of diplazontines as their

distribution ranges often show large overlap; genetic differences thus cannot be explained by geographic isolation but are indicative of independently evolving lineages (De Queiroz 2007). In several cases, however, the gene trees did not reflect morphology very well, even in the case of the barcoding locus CO1.

To explore the limits of DNA barcoding in parasitoid wasps, we investigated the case of the genus *Diplazon* (paper 4). An automated approach of DNA barcoding only recognized ten out of the sixteen species that can be delimited using morphological characters, and several species that are clearly distinct morphologically share identical barcodes. We used morphometrics to support the species hypotheses obtained from discrete morphological characters, sequenced the nuclear, fast-evolving gene ITS2 as a complement to CO1, and used a PCR approach to screen the wasps for endosymbiotic bacteria of the *Wolbachia pipientis* group. These bacteria probably infect a majority of arthropod species and are known to manipulate their reproductive biology in order to enhance their own transmission via the cytoplasm of the egg (Werren et al. 2008). It has long been assumed that they might cause distortions in the diversity patterns of mitochondrial DNA, especially in the presence of rare hybridization events during which *Wolbachia* could pass between species. The numerous reviews that discuss this mechanism of endosymbiont-mediated mtDNA introgression (e.g., Johnstone and Hurst 1996, Ballard and Rand 2005, Hurst and Jiggins 2005, Galtier et al. 2009) draw on very few convincing empirical examples. For a study to provide plausible evidence for the role of an endosymbiont in facilitating mtDNA introgression, it needs to include both donor and recipient species and demonstrate a strict association of both their mtDNA and endosymbiont strains. To our knowledge, there are currently only six studies that fulfil these requirements (Ballard 2000, Jiggins 2003, Narita et al. 2006, Whitworth et al. 2007, Gompert et al. 2008, Raychoudhury et al. 2009). In our study of *Diplazon* and *Wolbachia*, we provide evidence for such endosymbiont-mediated mtDNA introgression and thus contribute to the knowledge about causes for the failure of DNA barcoding to correctly identify biological species.

In a collaborative study on ecological speciation in a complex of parasitic wasps that attack their beetle hosts in granaries (paper 5), we investigated the ecology, host choice, early learning, and morphological and molecular differentiation of two host strains. We found that the ability of one of the potential species to learn their host's odour upon emergence might have facilitated the speciation process. Furthermore, even though the two host races can currently not be identified using discrete morphological or morphometric characters, they are clearly distinct on one mitochondrial and five nuclear genetic markers that we amplified. In terms of species delimitation, the use of three intronic markers represents an especially promising advancement as introns are a very abundant source of information throughout the genome that is only rarely used in species delimitation in parasitoids. Previous approaches relied heavily on mitochondrial DNA because of higher average substitution rates, but nuclear introns have the advantage of potentially yielding several independently segregating markers. They can thus provide the basis for a direct test of the amount of gene flow between putative species through models such as the multi-species coalescent (Yang and Rannala 2010). I established the intron markers in a lab in Stockholm relying on a whole-genome comparison conducted between the nine available hymenopteran genomes (Hartig et al. 2012); this approach is very promising for future studies that aim to establish sound molecular species delimitations that are indicative of independently evolving lineages, as is the case in most species concepts (De Queiroz 2007).

Conclusions

Taxonomy has to aim to produce vigorous species hypotheses which stand on a sound basis both in terms of data and theory. Species form as the result of numerous historical, ecological, and genetic factors and thus represent inherently complex entities that can only be diagnosed properly when information from different sources is integrated. Morphological characters are to a large extent of multigenic origin and, if carefully recorded and decisive, should thus be preferred over a single-gene approach such as DNA barcoding under almost every species concept (De Queiroz 2007). Our finding of endosymbiont-mediated transfer of DNA between two species of *Diplazon* further underlines the importance of independent lines of evidence for species delimitation, and the development of intron markers allows for approaches which directly assess whether two groups really represent independently evolving lineages, which is the basis of most species concepts including the unified species concept (De Queiroz 2007). Integrative taxonomy of course comes at a cost and requires taxonomic expertise, but is the only scientifically justifiable answer to the taxonomic impediment (Schlick-Steiner et al. 2010).

Phylogenetics for evolutionary research

Background

Phylogenies are just as much at the heart of evolutionary thought as the process of natural selection is. The insight that all life on earth goes back to a common ancestor has thrust us humans from the throne of creation and thus was in many ways the implication from Darwin's seminal work (Darwin 1859) which was hardest to accept for his contemporaries (Owen 1859, Huxley 1863). But the explanatory power of common descent is so great that it quickly started reaching into all fields of organismic biology, from studies of development to adaptation research and nowadays genomics. This fact is summarized in a quote from a meeting of the Society of Systematic Biologists, "nothing makes sense in evolution except in the light of phylogeny" (Sterelny and Griffiths 1999). Phylogenies underpin classifications in that they enable the definition of natural groups. They allow for proper statistical treatment in comparative studies where the non-independence of different species as data points because of their common history needs to be accounted for (Felsenstein 1985). They facilitate evolutionary biology by providing information about character history and polarity and thus allow asking the right adaptive questions. As an example, one might ask why the European oak trees drop their leaves so late in autumn when all other deciduous trees are already bare of leaves; however, the oak phylogeny tells us that the European oaks developed from evergreen ancestors (Manos et al. 1999), so the evolutionary novelty is not prolonged retention of the leaves but dropping them at all, for which it is simple to find an adaptive explanation.

Despite the appeal of phylogenies as tools for understanding evolution, our knowledge of the tree of life is still very incomplete, and this is mostly due to the complexity of evolution itself. Morphological characters often evolved in a highly punctuated fashion and thus left many gaps both in the fossil record and among the living species, and these gaps hamper our understanding of evolutionary trajectories (Eldredge and Gould 1972, Pennell et al. 2014). Molecular sequences partly remedied these shortcomings, but even they do not fit the gradual evolutionary models commonly used to reconstruct their history very well (Pagel et al. 2006). And there are other processes that impede phylogeny reconstruction, such as substitution saturation erasing phylogenetic signal (Simon et al. 1994), difficult alignment and thus homology statement for DNA and amino acid sequences (Phillips et al. 2000, Morrison 2009), convergence on the molecular level (Christin et al. 2007),

uneven base composition (Jermini et al. 2004), hybridization and lateral gene transfer (Mallet 2005, Stern et al. 2010), and differences between gene-trees and species-trees due to population processes leading to incomplete lineage sorting (Edwards 2009). Studies based on single or few genes thus cannot be trusted unless independent data is available to corroborate the results, and as a consequence, datasets are currently growing in parallel with decreasing sequencing costs and improved analysis methodologies (McCormack et al. 2013).

Model-based phylogenetics including maximum likelihood and Bayesian inference (Ronquist and Deans 2010) have an unprecedented power when it comes to inferring the past, as their rigorous statistical basis and inherent flexibility not only provide the most rigorous phylogenetic hypotheses, but also allow answering complex evolutionary questions, e.g., via model-testing approaches (Knudsen and Miyamoto 2001, Matz and Nielsen 2005, Sullivan and Joyce 2005, Goldberg and Igic 2008). Progress has been made in terms of further development of evolutionary models for DNA characters (Jayaswal et al. 2011, Dutheil et al. 2012), and powerful models have been suggested for all types of data, from morphology, behaviour, and ecology to proteins and genome architecture (Lewis 2001a, Blanquart and Lartillot 2006, Alekseyenko et al. 2008, Boussau et al. 2008). The problem of incongruent gene trees can now be remedied by modelling the population processes behind incomplete lineage sorting (Edwards et al. 2007, Liu et al. 2008), and multiple-sequence alignments can be improved by simultaneous tree reconstruction (Redelings and Suchard 2005, Kjer et al. 2007). But further advances are sorely needed, as the development of sufficiently realistic evolutionary models still lags strongly behind the datasets that become available with the dawn of the genomic era.

The role of morphology in phylogenetics is nowadays mostly viewed as marginal. However, there are two areas where its importance is undisputed, i.e., when fossils are included in order to infer their relationships among each other or with extant taxa and when the interest is actually in the evolution of specific morphological traits (e.g., Broad and Quicke 2000, Klopstein et al. 2010, Slater et al. 2012). Furthermore, morphological data is often still included in higher-level phylogenetic analyses if the molecular data is indecisive.

Own work

The tree of life of the insect order Hymenoptera is one example of a difficult phylogenetic problem due to a presumably very rapid radiation giving rise to most currently recognized superfamilies during the Mesozoic (Sharkey 2007). Funded by the Tree of Life project of the U.S. National Science Foundation, hymenopteran experts from around the world collaborated to propose a well-supported phylogeny of the group (Heraty et al. 2011, Sharkey et al. 2012). However, multiple sequence alignment proved difficult and the tree in part remained poorly resolved.

In paper 6, we suggest an improved tree by adding several nuclear, protein-coding genes to the dataset and by improving the analysis methodology, especially in terms of alignment and the combined analysis of morphology and sequence data in a Bayesian framework. Alignment strategy indeed had a large impact on the resulting phylogeny, and earlier studies might have suffered from inflated support values due to partly subjective multiple-sequence alignments. We compared a purely objective, non-parametric alignment method (Kato et al. 2009) with a Bayesian approach which models insertion and deletion events and thus simultaneously aligns the sequences and constructs the phylogeny (Suchard and Redelings 2006). The high parameterization of the method does unfortunately not allow running a full analysis with a larger number of terminals, and we resorted to a step-wise procedure aligning subsets of more closely related taxa and later combining

the resulting alignments into a master alignment (Wheeler and Kececioglu 2007). Independent of alignment strategy, we could confirm several relationships that have been suggested earlier and could explore conflict between different data partitions. But even though we used seven genes amounting to a total of 9'000 bp, we could not resolve the complete tree, and many nodes remained controversial between data partition or analysis methodology. This study exemplifies the limits of few-gene approaches using Sanger sequencing, even if combined with morphology; it turned out that both data partitions were in most cases indecisive about the same parts of the phylogeny. We can expect that next-generation sequencing data will soon be available to test our results and hopefully resolve some of the remaining questions about the hymenopteran tree.

Even though the phylogeny of the hymenopteran superfamilies is not entirely resolved, it can still be used to infer evolutionary patterns, especially in the Bayesian context which allows integrating over phylogenetic uncertainty (Ronquist and Deans 2010). We made use of this option to study the history of loss and gain of introns (paper 7). Intron-exon structure is often referred to as part of the “genome's morphology” (cit) and can be analysed using morphological evolutionary models. The issue of intron-exon structure arose when amplifying the nuclear protein-coding gene elongation factor 1- α in a PCR approach and finding that the two copies (F1 and F2) of this gene found previously in some groups are present in all Hymenoptera (Danforth and Ji 1998). The elongation factor is involved in protein synthesis where it is responsible for delivering aminoacylated tRNAs to the ribosome during translation (Andersen et al. 2003), but it is also known to serve other functions, e.g., in protein degradation, regulation of cytoskeletal rearrangements, viral propagation, and apoptosis (Mateyak and Kinzy 2010). Using the hymenopteran phylogeny, we could show that the two copies evolve independently and both seem to be functional, with regions of differences in their amino-acid sequences located around potentially active protein areas. We found a total of seven different intron positions along the gene, with some introns present only in a few and others in a majority or even all taxa; however, the intron used earlier to distinguish the F1 from the F2 copy is not present in all taxa. Using a simple Markov model to estimate rates of intron gain and loss, we find relatively high rates both of gains and of losses and establish several cases of convergent intron gain at identical positions. This result can be explained by canonical motives present at most intron positions, so-called proto-splice sites (Dibb and Newman 1989), which act as preferred sites for intron insertion and/or retention. This puts a constraint on the sites available for intron insertion and increases the probability of them arising convergently. Intron-exon structure is thus not a very reliable predictor of orthology, and the copies of elongation-factor 1- α in Hymenoptera should thus be distinguished based on comparison with entire sequences and not intron-exon structure. And our results suggest that the dynamics and speed of intron evolution might have been underestimated in the past.

Using similar evolutionary models, we also traced the evolution of morphological and ecological characteristics in a group of parasitic wasps (paper 8). We used a three-gene phylogeny of *Ichneumon* parasitoids to derive a first evolutionary hypothesis for the genus, study changes in host ranges, and test for correlated evolution between body shape and host ecology. *Ichneumon* species attack the pupae of butterflies and moths and are mostly generalists found on several genera within one or a few host families. They seem to be adapted more to a host's habitat and especially the place it pupates than to the phylogenetic position of the host (Hinz and Horstmann 2007), which seems likely given that although they are internal parasitoids, they spend very little time inside the host pupa. Furthermore, insects have reduced levels of immune defence during the pupal stage and physiologically, a wasp might thus be able to cope with a large range of hosts. However, many

lepidopteran pupae are well hidden, and finding them might put a stronger constraint on a wasp then successfully developing inside it does. Comparing the body shape of *Ichneumon* females with pupation sites of their hosts, we found a striking pattern, with the stout species with short antennae attacking hosts that pupate in the leaf litter or in burrows below ground, while the females with antennae of normal length attack pupae in the vegetation. A phylogenetic test for correlated evolution of these characters (Pagel and Meade 2006) confirmed our expectation of body shapes likely being the result of an adaptation to host searching.

Conclusions

Phylogenies represent powerful tools for reconstructing evolutionary trajectories and test adaptive scenarios. They provide a context for interpreting ecological differences between species and trace their diversification through time. Even though this realization is as old as evolutionary theory itself, recent and ongoing developments in both the molecular and theoretical fields are only starting to uncover the full potential of this approach. The availability of molecular datasets of ever-increasing size improves our understanding of phylogenetic relationships and has the potential to fill most of the gaps in our knowledge of insect evolution (e.g., Misof et al. 2014). Decreasing sequencing costs and the development of elaborate genome-reduction techniques, such as transcriptome sequencing or target-enrichment protocols (McCormack et al. 2013), make next-generation sequencing available even for non-model taxa and dense taxon-sampling strategies. Uncertainty about phylogenetic relationships will thus further diminish in the near future and the accuracy of the estimates of relative branch lengths will increase, which allows us to ask more detailed and complex questions about the evolutionary history of life. At the same time, advances in statistical approaches facilitate the use of phylogenies for evolutionary inference. The two examples in this thesis, i.e., the dynamics of intron gain and loss and morphological adaptations to host ecology, were based on comparatively simple models of character evolution, but a lot of progress is currently made on improving such models by adding realism and complexity. This is facilitated also by developments in bioinformatics, especially in the Bayesian computer program RevBayes which relies on graphical models (Höhna et al. 2014) and allows the user to reflect complex evolutionary scenarios in phylogenetic models that can then be inferred and tested. The combination of molecular biology, organism ecology, and bioinformatics has the potential to make a tremendous addition to our understanding of the evolution of life on earth, especially when complemented with insights from palaeontology.

Advances in molecular dating

Background

Systematics already interacted intensely with palaeontology before the molecular revolution, mostly by comparing the morphologies of recent and extinct taxa and deriving hypotheses about character evolution and homologies. Morphology-based phylogenies provided a framework for studying the relationships among fossil taxa and allowed estimating the level of incompleteness of the fossil record (Wills 2001). But with the proposition of the molecular clock hypothesis (Zuckerkandl and Pauling 1962) and its theoretical underpinning by the neutral theory (Kimura 1968), the interplay became even more intense. Dating molecular trees allows investigating the evolution of a particular group in the light of geological, climatic, and biotic circumstances and informs studies of biogeography, co-evolution, and diversification. The explanatory power of a well-dated phylogeny is

thus tremendous, but especially during the early phase of molecular phylogenetics, problems with molecular dating were to a large extent ignored. Results which strongly contradicted previous assumptions about the ages of different groups were accepted too easily (e.g., Hedges et al. 1996, Wang et al. 1999) which led to a perceived conflict between palaeontologists and molecular phylogeneticists (Donoghue and Benton 2007). First came the realization that single genes often show a lot of variation in their evolutionary rates among branches of the tree; indeed, using adequate tests, the hypothesis of a strict molecular clock can be rejected on a majority of trees which span a larger set of taxa. This realization led to the development of so-called "relaxed clocks", i.e., models which allow for among-lineage rate variation (Sanderson 1997, Thorne and Kishino 2002, Drummond et al. 2006, Lepage et al. 2007). In parallel, using an estimate for the evolutionary rate derived from a group which is only distantly related is discouraged, even though this fixed-rate approach still enjoys great popularity in studies of closely related taxa (Papadopoulou et al. 2010). The second line of criticism concerns the calibrations used to obtain absolute evolutionary rates, i.e., in time units instead of substitutions. Such calibrations are typically derived either from geological events in connection with a biogeographic hypothesis, for instance by interpreting recent distribution patterns in terms of vicariance events, or using the fossil record. Both approaches can be prone to misinterpretation and at the least, uncertainty in time estimates of geological events and fossil ages should be accounted for (Parham et al. 2012). The Bayesian statistical framework provides large flexibility in the way geological or fossil information enters the analysis, and uncertainty in calibration points can in theory be accounted for (Yang and Rannala 2006). However, the secondary interpretations necessary for deriving calibration points still needed to make lots of assumptions. For fossil calibrations, the standard approach is to assign one or ideally several fossils to specific nodes in a tree of the extant taxa. Because fossils only provide minimum node ages, the choice of a prior distribution on the age of those nodes is to a large extent arbitrary and has been shown to have a very high impact on the resulting divergence time estimates (Inoue et al. 2010). A new approach which does not treat fossils as priors on node ages, but instead includes them as primary data points via the coding of their morphological features into a matrix (Ronquist et al. 2012) offers a more scientifically justifiable and thus probably more accurate and precise way of calibrating trees.

Own work

Examples for the limitations of the calibration or 'node-dating' method are numerous, but for most groups, no other divergence-time estimates are currently available. In a collaborative study of the radiation of song birds (Passeriformes, paper 9), we used seven nuclear genes and a relaxed-clock model in combination with one geological and five fossil calibrations. The geological calibration was based on the assumption of a vicariance event which separated the New Zealand wrens (Acanthisittidae) from all other passerines. However, the exact timing and speed of the separation between New Zealand and Australia during the Cretaceous is still under debate, and earlier studies might have relied on an unrealistically old and narrow time interval for this event. The fossil calibrations we used represent the best-preserved and best-placed fossil Passeriformes and provided well-justified minimum age constraints on five separate nodes. However, as in any other node dating study, we had to come up with likely averages on the node age prior, for which the evidence is less decisive. We investigated the sensitivity of the divergence-time estimates to the priors on the node ages and found that they to a large extent depended on the interpretation of the vicariance calibration. The sensitivity of the resulting ages to our prior settings makes any ecological and palaeontological interpretation problematic.

An improvement to this situation is likely to result from the new 'total-evidence dating' approach that we and another study introduced a few years ago (paper 10, Pyron 2011). This approach treats fossils as terminals instead of as priors on node ages (Fig. 2); morphological evidence from the fossils is thus directly exposed to the analysis, which results in a more robust and scientifically sound way of using the fossil evidence to calibrate molecular phylogenies. In addition, total-evidence dating can make use of the whole fossil record of a group instead of only of the oldest fossils that can be associated without reasonable doubt with one specific node as in node dating. We applied the approach to the early evolution of the insect order Hymenoptera using 8 kb of molecular data from 68 extant taxa and 353 morphological characters scored for both the extant taxa and for 45 mostly Mesozoic fossils. In parallel, we used these fossils to derive calibration points for a node-dating approach so that we could make a direct comparison between the two methods. Age estimates from total-evidence dating were both more precise and less dependent on prior assumptions and thus likely also more accurate. And most of all, this new approach puts the emphasis in molecular dating back to where it belongs, in the careful empirical study of the fossil record (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Comparison between the standard node-dating and the newly proposed total-evidence dating approach. In node-dating, fossils are placed on the tree based on their morphology and several usually untested assumptions about morphological evolution. Even assuming a certain placement of the fossil, it only provides a minimum age for the node in question; a largely arbitrary prior distribution on the age of the node has to also be assumed. In total-evidence dating, the fossil is integrated into the analysis via a morphological matrix that also contains the extant taxa. Its position in the tree and the ages of the nodes are inferred directly from the data, avoiding secondary interpretations of the fossil record.

As total-evidence dating is a very young method, major questions about its performance and applicability remain open. Using the Hymenoptera dataset, we focussed on the impact of the tree prior by using more realistic depictions of the fossilization process (paper 11). The tree prior used in the original analysis was a simple uniform prior which assumes that each tree topology is *a priori* equally likely, and that the branch lengths follow a uniform distribution. This uniform tree prior has previously been used on non-clock trees and was adapted by us to clock-trees with taxa sampled through time, thus allowing for the inclusion of fossils (paper 10). A more elaborate tree prior in the context of clock trees is the birth-death prior, a parametric prior under a model of cladogenesis. In its

simplest version, the birth-death process has two parameters, the birth rate (or speciation rate) giving rise to new lineages and the death rate (or extinction rate) governing their loss (Kendall 1948, Nee 2006). It has been extended recently to include fossils (Stadler 2010) and to allow for piece-wise changes in those rates (Gavryushkina et al. 2014). The fact that phylogenies are usually incompletely sampled, with only a subset of the extant species included, can be accounted for by specifying the sampling fraction and assuming that sampling was either random or by maximizing the phylogenetic diversity, for instance when including one species per genus or per family (Höhna 2011). We used the fossilized birth-death tree prior on our Hymenoptera dataset and investigated the impact of different prior settings and sampling strategies on the resulting divergence-time estimates in total-evidence dating. The impact of the sampling strategy was very large, with diversified sampling resulting in age estimates which were dozens of million years younger and in better agreement with the fossil record. Further studies of other datasets and of simulated data are needed to shed light on the reasons for this large impact of the tree prior, but our study demonstrates the importance of using realistic priors including adequate models of the sampling strategy.

Morphological phylogenetics is currently experiencing a revival because of its significance in total-evidence dating, but models of morphological evolution are still in their infancy. The standard Markov model for morphology (Lewis 2001a) assumes stationarity, which means that the character-state distribution remains the same across the phylogenetic tree. This assumption might not hold in the case of many morphological characters, which often show directional patterns. As a test case, we used wing veins, muscles, and sclerites in Hymenoptera (paper 12). Fossil evidence points to a role of directionality at least in wing veins, with the most complete venation known from the oldest fossils and with many extant taxa showing largely reduced venation. To capture directional patterns, we implemented a simple non-stationary Markov model which allows for different state frequencies at the root of the tree in the computer program MrBayes 3.2. The model was complemented by a reversible-jump move to the stationary model, which allows for direct model testing in the Bayesian framework. Using simulated data, we established the conditions under which directional evolution can be distinguished from the stationary case based on extant taxa only and found that even though a lot of the signal for directionality is erased rather quickly, conditions such as uneven branch lengths and unbalanced trees with many taxa still allow for the correct inference of directional evolution. We then applied the directional model to the hymenopteran dataset with and without fossils and found that it was strongly preferred over the stationary model for wing veins and muscles, which both apparently underwent a history of reduction towards the present. Applying the model to total-evidence dating, we found that accounting for directionality leads to more precise age estimates, which makes it a very promising extension to the currently available models of morphological evolution.

Conclusions

Molecular dating has until recently been based exclusively on the node-dating approach which relies on partly arbitrary interpretations of the fossil record. This situation has not improved its credibility and provoked numerous critique papers with titles such as "reading the entrails of chickens" (Graur and Martin 2004) or "the dating game" (Whitfield 2007). Total-evidence dating (Ronquist et al. 2012) directly includes the morphological evidence from the fossil record and thus integrates over the uncertainty of their placement in the tree. A model of morphological evolution provides branch lengths to the fossils which, in combination with information about the age of the strata where they have been found, calibrate the tree. This approach has the potential to put

molecular dating on a more robust scientific basis and has thus been received rather enthusiastically by the scientific community. However, many questions remain open about this rather new approach. Maybe the most pressing issue is the existence of a morphological clock, which is the most important assumption behind total-evidence dating. However, morphological characters are believed to exhibit higher levels of convergence, a more punctuated mode of evolution, and thus lower fit to stochastic models than molecular data (Wortley and Scotland 2006), and this might be especially true for clock models. But only very few studies have examined this with actual data, and it is unclear how clock-like the evolution of a dataset needs to be for it to still be able to inform dating studies, as relaxed-clock models might be able to capture much of the deviations. Another question relates to the extent of linkage between morphological and molecular branch lengths; once more, it is possible to unlink the relaxed-clock models and thus relative branch lengths between the molecular and the morphological partition, but a lot of power might be lost by doing so. Models which better capture the features of morphological data could also improve their clock-likeness. A combination of simulation studies and empirical research is needed to tackle these questions and will facilitate a more informed approach to total-evidence dating in the future. In any case, this method has already changed the field of molecular dating by stimulating fruitful discussions about the interplay of fossils and molecular trees and by provoking renewed interest in morphological phylogenetics.

List of papers included in habilitation thesis

Species discovery and the roles of morphology and DNA

1. **Klopfstein, S.** (2014): Review of the Diplazontinae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) of the Kuril islands, with descriptions of two new species. *Zootaxa*. 3779(1): 20-32.
2. **Klopfstein, S.** (in press): Nine new species of *Dimophora* from Australia (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae): new insights on the distribution of a poorly known genus of parasitoid wasps. *Austral Entomology*.
3. **Klopfstein, S.** (2014): Revision of the Western Palaearctic Diplazontinae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). *Zootaxa* 3801(1): 1-143.
4. **Klopfstein, S.**, Kropf, C., Baur, H. (in press): *Wolbachia* endosymbionts distort DNA barcoding in the parasitoid wasp genus *Diplazon* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*.
5. König, K., Krimmer, E., Brose, S., Ganter, C., Buschlüter, I., König, C., **Klopfstein, S.**, Wendt, I., Baur, H., Krogmann, L., Steidle, J.L.M. (2015): Does early learning drive ecological divergence during speciation processes in parasitoid wasps? *Proc R Soc B* 282: 20141850.

Phylogenetics for evolutionary research

6. **Klopfstein, S.**, L. Vilhelmsen, J. Heraty, M. Sharkey, F. Ronquist (2013): The hymenopteran tree of life: evidence from protein-coding genes and objectively aligned ribosomal data. *PLoS One* 8(8): e69344.
7. **Klopfstein, S.**, Ronquist, F. (2013): Convergent intron gains in hymenopteran elongation factor-1 α . *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 67 (1): 266-276.
8. Tschopp, A., Riedel, M., Kropf, C., Nentwig, W., **Klopfstein, S.** (2013): The evolution of host associations in the parasitic wasp genus *Ichneumon* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae): convergent adaptations to host pupation sites. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 13:74.

Advances in molecular dating

9. Ericson, P.G.P., **Klopstein, S.**, Irestedt, M., Nguyen, J.M.T., Nylander, J.A.A. (2014): Dating the diversification of the major lineages of Passeriformes (Aves). *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 14:8.
10. Ronquist*, F., **S. Klopstein***, L. Vilhelmsen, S. Schulmeister, D.L. Murray, A.P. Rasnitsyn (2012): A total-evidence approach to dating with fossils, applied to the early radiation of the Hymenoptera. *Systematic Biology*. 61(6), 973–999. (*equal contribution).
11. Zhang, C., Stadler, T., **Klopstein, S.**, Heath, T., Ronquist, F. (in press): Total-Evidence Dating under the Fossilized Birth-Death Process. *Systematic Biology*.
12. **Klopstein, S.**, Vilhelmsen, L., Ronquist, F. (2015): A non-stationary Markov model detects directional evolution in hymenopteran morphology. *Systematic Biology* 64(6): 1089-1103.

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